

Results of a study at the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical indicated that seed can be cleaned completely by exposing it for 6 d to a dry heat of 65 °C. This treatment was lethal when first applied to Burundi-cultivated Yunnan 3. Further studies using six cultivars showed that indicas Ambalalava, Facagro 59, and Kirundo 9 endured the treatment without problems but that viability progressively decreased among the japonicas. After 6 d of the treatment, viability decreased by about 20% for CR1009 and Kirundo 3 and more than

60% for Yunnan 3 (see figure). Results confirmed that heat treatment eradicated *P. fuscovaginatae* from the seed (data not shown).

The discordance in germination for Yunnan 3 in the tests was attributed to seed age. The natural germination rate dropped by half for year-old seed, and the sensitiveness to heat increased so that less than 5% of the seeds germinated after the treatment. After 2 yr, the few seeds still viable were killed by temperature (see table). Seed moisture levels were also

tested, but they did not affect germination ability.

The effects of disinfecting seeds for BSR in the fields at rice maturity were minimal because of the apparently ubiquitous distribution of the bacteria; their survival in the ground, on crop residues, and on other cultures and weeds; and their easy transmission among plants. Heat treatment—subject to a few precautions—is recommended to prevent the spread of BSR during germplasm exchange. ■

Relationship between tungro (RTD) infection and water level in direct seeded rice

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Infection rate of RTD in direct seeded rice has been reported to be less than in transplanted rice. We examined tungro virus infection in rice direct seeded in different water depths in 1992 wet season.

The 3- x 7-m plots were laid out in split-plot design (main plot = water depth, subplot = variety) with four replications. Ten varieties, two of which were coated

with the oxygen-release chemical Calper to improve crop establishment, were broadcast at 200 seeds/m² onto puddled fields. Water depths of 0, 5, and 10 cm were maintained for 21 d, after which flooding was a uniform 5 cm. Rice plants emerged from 0 cm water at 3-5 d after seeding (DAS), from 5 cm at 6-9 DAS, and from 10 cm at 6-10 DAS. Carbofuran granule was applied at 1 kg active ingredient (ai)/ha at 1 and 34 DAS, and 2,4-D emulsifiable concentrate (EC) at 0.8 kg ai/ha at 28 DAS. Weed infestation in nonflooded plots was about 7 times higher than in flooded plots at 28 DAS (240 vs 1700 weeds/m²).

RTD incidence was scored visually at

56 DAS. We determined infection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) by collecting 24 samples in a W-pattern from each replication at 78 DAS and indexing by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

RTD symptoms were not observed in nonflooded plots, but were severe in flooded plots. More plants were infected with RTBV and RTSV in flooded plots than in nonflooded plots (see table). Three varieties showed low infection rate and may harbor resistance to the vector. Results indicate that susceptible varieties incur higher RTD infection in direct seeded rice culture with flooding than without flooding. ■

Tungro incidence and percentage of infection of RTBV and RTSV in direct seeded rice in different depths of water.^a

Variety	Tungro incidence ^b (score)			RTBV (%)			RTSV (%)		
	Water depth (cm)								
	0	5	10	0	5	10	0	5	10
ASD 1	0.0 bU	7.8 aUV	6.5 aVW	2 bW	28 aWX	80 aWX	32 aW	96 aW	94 aW
ASD 1 (coated)	0.0 bU	6.0 aVW	7.0 aUV	2 bW	21 aXY	71 aWX	41 aW	91 aW	99 aW
Chin-Chan	0.0 bU	0.8 aY	0.8 aY	8 bW	53 aWX	81 aWX	39 aW	93 aW	100 aW
IR50	0.0 bU	6.5 aVW	6.5 aUV	0 cW	32 bXY	97 aW	4 bY	94 aW	99 aW
IR50 (coated)	0.0 bU	6.5 aVW	7.0 aUV	1 bW	30 aXY	69 aWX	13 bXY	91 aW	96 aW
Caloro/Blue Rose	0.0 bU	8.8 aU	8.5 aU	1 bW	88 aW	95 aW	35 aW	98 aW	96 aW
IR31802-48-2-2-2	0.0 bU	5.3 aW	4.8 aW	3 bW	37 aWX	63 aWX	24 aWX	71 aW	71 aWX
CO 25	0.0 aU	0.3 aZ	0.0 aZ	3 bW	21 aXY	57 aWXY	17 bXY	35 aW	51 abXY
IR36	0.0 bU	2.0 aX	1.8 aX	0 bW	40 aWX	52 aXYZ	7 bXY	88 aW	86 aW
Farangey	0.0 aU	0.0 aZ	0.0 aZ	0 bW	3 abZ	9 aYZ	4 aY	2 aX	17 aZ
IR41996-50-2-1-3	0.0 aU	0.0 aZ	0.0 aZ	3 aW	5 aYZ	7 aZ	8 bY	27 aW	32 aXY
BR1870-89-1-1	0.0 aU	0.0 aZ	0.0 aZ	0 bW	3 abZ	15 aYZ	3 aY	3 aX	9 aYZ
Mean of top nine	0.0 b	4.9 a	4.8 a	2 c	39 b	74 a	24 b	84 a	88 a
Mean of bottom three	0.0 a	0.0 a	0.0 a	1 b	4 ab	10 a	5 b	11 a	19 a

^aMeans having a common letter in columns (UVWXYZ) and sections of row (abc) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bVisual scoring: 0 = no infection, 1 = trace to ~ 1%, 2 = ~ 5%, 3 = ~ 10%, 4 = ~ 20%, 5 = ~ 30%, 6 = ~ 40%, 7 = ~ 60%, 8 = ~ 80%, 9 = ~ 100%.